

Curriculum vitae

Personnal informations

First name: Samir

Last name: Hachani

Date and place of birth: November 6th 1958 -Tunis (Tunisia)

Citizenship: Algerian

Address: Cite des 800 logements Bt.1 Apt.6 – La Fontan (Bouzareah) , Algiers (Algeria)

Marital status: married, two kids

Personal cellular phone: 00 213 770 79 95 53

Home phone : 00 213 23 25 60 84

E-mail : sam_hac1@yahoo.fr

Education :

PhD Library and Documentary Science (Algiers'University II) 2013

Magister Library and Documentary Science (Algiers'University) 2001

Master of Science in Library Science (School of Library and Information Management-University of Southern California – Los Angeles) 1986

Bachelor in Library and Documentary Science (Algiers 'University) 1982

Degree of graduation from secondary studies (baccalaureate) Emir Abd-el-Kader High School 1978

Professionnal Expérience

Lecturer at *The School of Library Information and Documentary Sciences – Algiers'* University since 1991

Teacher at *The Centre d'Etudes et de Recherche en Information Scientifique et Technique (CERIST)* in 1992/1993

Teacher at *The University of Continuous Training (UFC)* since 1991

Member of *Laboratoire de traduction du Centre National de Recherches sur le Mouvement National et la Revolution du 1^{er} Novembre 1954*

Member of *The Association Internationale des Francophone des Bibliothécaires et Documentalistes (AIFBD)*

Member of *The Arab Federation of Library and Information (AFLI)*

Vice President of *Association Science et Bien Communs (ASBC)* Québec (Canada)

Personnal abilities

Speak Arabic, French and English fluently. Possesses also a good ability in Spanish.

Good computer abilities

Publications

Contribution de la bibliothèque de l'Université d'Alger à l'arabisation de l'enseignement supérieur , Schéma et Schématisation : Revue internationale de bibliologie, Numéro spécial : La Bibliologie politique en Algérie, n° 63, p.46-57, 4th quater 2005.

Les Archives ouvertes : un nouvel essor pour la recherche académique paper presented at Le Colloque national sur la numérisation des bibliothèques universitaires, organized by Le Laboratoire d'Etudes et de Recherche sur l'Information Scientifique et Technique (L.E.R.I.S.T.), Université Mentouri (Constantine) (Algeria), May 6-8th 2006.

Bibliothèque numérique et droits d'auteurs : un délicat compromis paper presented for an awareness day organized by La Bibliothèque Nationale d'Algérie under the theme " Journée sur la Bibliothèque virtuelle et le nouveau savoir", June 2006

From paper to digital: The Algiers' University library experience in digitizing its holdings (in Arabic), paper presented at the 18th Arab Federation of Library and Information (A.F.L.I.), Jeddah (Saudi Arabia), November 17-20th 2007.

Webreview : Un exemple de libre accès du Sud paper presented at Journées d'études under the theme *Internet et les SHS*, organized by Le Centre National de Recherches Préhistoriques, Anthropologiques et Historiques (C.N.R.P.A.H.),Alger, October 17-18th 2012

De quelques exemples de contrôle par les pairs ouverts : F 1000, A.C.P. et E.T.A.I. paper presented at 81^e Congrès de l'ACFAS, Université Laval (Quebec), May 6-8th 2013

Libre accès et contrôle par les pairs: une inéluctable et nécessaire convergence " paper presented at The World Social Science Forum 2013 - " Social Transformations and the Digital Age ", Montréal, October 13-15th 2013

Exemples de programmes de la résorption de la fracture numérique et ses effets sur le libre accès en Afrique sub saharienne : Cap Vert, Botswana, Ile Maurice paper presented at the 82nd Congres de l'ACFAS, Concordia Université, Montréal, May 12-16th 2014

Who's the peer in a networked world ? paper presented at 1st International Symposium on Philosophy and Library and Information Science(I.S.P.L.I.S.), Ethics : theory and practice, Kastamonu (Turkey), September 3-5th 2014

Politique (s) du libre acces en Algérie : état des lieux et perspectives , paper presented at I.C.O.A. 2014 : International Conference on Open Access and scientific research: towards new values , Tunis (Tunisia) , November 27 -28th 2014

Science is a common good ! Experience of two NGOs and perspectives for action, Workshop presented with Remi Barré at The World Forum on Science and Democracy, Tunis, March 24-27th 2015

Algerian universities' open repositories: an output for indigenous science made by academic institutions in Algeria in creating and managing open repositories, 7th

Quantitative and Qualitative Methods in Libraries (Q.Q.M.L.), Paris (France) , May 26-29th 2015

Open peer review: fast forward for a new science In Anne Woodsworth , W. David Penniman (Eds.) *Advances in Librarianship , Current Issues in Libraries, Information Science and Related Fields*, Volume 39, p.115 – 141, June 2015

L'Open Peer Review , petite ou grande révolution dans le monde de l'édition scientifique ? paper presented at Open Access Week 2015 , Laval University (Québec), October 20-22nd 2015

African repositories in The Ranking Web of Repositories : A comparative analysis of their standing in DOAR and ROAR, paper presented at International Knowledge Conference (I.K.C.) 2015, Kuching (Sarawak - Malaysia), November 15 – 18th 2015

Open peer review workshop ” workshop ran with Daniel Mietchen and Neil Chue Hong, Force 2016, “ *Building bridges, connecting knowledge* ” , Portland (Oregon) , April 17-19th 2016.

La Science est-elle foncièrement occidental - centriste? Quelques réflexions sur l'inclusion du savoir des Suds dans le corpus de la science , paper presented at the 84^e Congrès de l'ACFAS, Université du Québec A Montréal (U.Q.A.M.), Montréal, May 09-13th 2016

June's 1962 Algiers University arson: a bigger crime behind the fire , poster presented at The Joint Conference of the AIC's 44th Annual Meeting and CAC-ACCR 42nd Annual Conference under the theme : Preparing for disasters and confronting the unexpected in conservation, Montreal , May 13-17th 2016

A Bird's-eye view of two open access experiences in Algeria: CERIST's Webreview and Dépôt Numérique de l'Université d'Alger , IFLA/De Gruyter special volume “ Library and Information Science in the Middle East and North Africa ”, part of E.L.I.M.E. - 21 (Educating Librarians in the Middle East: building bridges for the 21st Century), Fellows Editing Volume on LIS in MENA, , July 2016

Faire du libre accès un outil de justice cognitive et d'empowerment des universitaires des pays des Suds = Open access as a tool of cognitive science and empowerment of academics from the Global South with Florence Piron [et al] , *Revue Maghrébine des sciences de l'information et de la documentation*, n°25, December 2016, p.91-106.

La Pratique des frais demandés aux auteurs par les revues en libre accès : une pratique pénalisante pour les pays du Sud, with Florence Piron, *Revue Maghrébine des sciences de l'information et de la documentation*, n°25, December 2016, p.215-237

La Fracture numérique nuit-elle aux possibles effets positifs du libre accès en Afrique ? Essai d'analyse et éléments de réponse In *Justice cognitive, libre accès et savoirs locaux*, au service de la science ouverte juste, Florence Piron, Samuel Regulus et Marie Sophie Dibounje Madiba Eds. , Québec, Éditions science et bien commun, 15 December 2016, p.107-124

Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia's presence in The Directory of Open Access Repositories (DOAR) and The Registry of Open Access Repositories (ROAR): A comparative study

of their ratio of open access material, Open Information Science/ De Gruyter, 1(1), p. 56-70.

Research Ideas and Outcomes journal (R.I.O.): A novel way to make science, paper presented at the 12th Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing, U.i.T., The Arctic University of Norway, Tromsø (Norway), November 22 – 23 2017

Open access in the Global South: The Maghrebi experience, poster presented at the Force 2018 conference, Montreal (Canada), October 10-13th 2018

The S.O.H.A. project: An open science project from the South, poster presented at the 13th Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing , UiT, The Arctic University of Norway, Tromsø (Norway), November 28–29, 2018

Les Pratiques d'évaluation par les pair-e-s : pas de neutralité In : Et si la recherche ne pouvait pas etre neutre ? Laurence Briere, Melissa Lieutenant – Gosselin and Florence Piron Eds., Quebec (Canada), Edition Science et Bien Communs, May 2019, p.95-113

When global is local: open scholarly communication in the Global South, F.S.C.I. 2019, Force 11 Scholarly Communication Institute,U.C.L.A., Los Angeles (California), August 05-09 2019, with Gimena del Rio Riande (Chair), Daniel O'Donnell and Idowu Adegbilero-Iwari